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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF ANTI ASTHMATIC ACTIVITY OF
ETHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACT OF CHLERODENDRUM
INERME**

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Abstract:

*In this study, investigate the anti asthmatic activity of the ethanolic leaf extract of Chlerodendrum inerme animal models using Histamine induce broncho constriction method. In which Animals are placed in an aerosol chamber and exposed to histamine or serotonin. The time it takes for the animal to collapse (asphyxial convulsion) is recorded. Protective drugs delay the onset of collapse. Antihistaminic activity was studied in guinea pigs using histamine-induced bronchospasm where preconvulsive dyspnea was used as an end point following exposure to histamine aerosol. It was evaluated for antihistamine and bronchodilator activities and it administrated at the doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg body weight. A dose response curve for histamine + Chlerodendrum inerme is lower, when compared with histamine induced contraction($p < 0.05$) at moderate dose level. The Chlerodendrum inerme at at the dose of 200mg significantly prolonged the latent period of convulsions as compared to control following the exposure of histamine aerosol. The result of present study shows that Chlerodendrum inerme significantly protected the Guinea pigs against histamine-induced bronchospasm. Significant increase in between pre and post treatment time (** $P < 0.01$). The present study reveals that the Chlerodendrum inerme can be more effective in the treatment of Bronchial asthma.*

Keywords: Chlerodendrum inerme (LM), asthma, anti-histaminic activity, bronchodilator activity

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INTRODUCTION:

'Asthma' is a Greek word which means 'breathless' or 'to breathe with open mouth' [1]. It is defined as 'a chronic inflammatory disorder of the airways associated with increased airway hyper-responsiveness, recurrent episodes breathlessness, coughing, chest particularly of wheezing, tightness, at and night/early morning [2]. Intensive research during the last several decades has highlighted the role of lymphocytes, immunoglobulins, mast cells, and various autacoids in the etiopathogenesis of allergic conditions [3, 4]. As a public health problem, asthma is an important allergic disorder. Prevalence of asthma is between 100 and 150 million people around the globe and India has an estimated 15-20 million asthmatics. This number is rising [5]. The total estimated burden of Asthma is an overall prevalence of 3% (30 million patients), and among adults over the age of 15, a median prevalence of 2.4% [6]. The cost of medication in India was estimated as US\$ 30 per month [7]. In siddha system of medicine asthma is analogues with 'Swasa kasam'. Many medicinal plants and herbo mineral preparations in siddha system used for the treatment of asthma (Swasa kasam) which have anti-inflammatory, immuno modulatory, antihistaminic, smooth-muscle relaxants and allergic activity. Drugs used were Histamine diphosphate (Sigma Chemical, USA) and Promethazine hydrochloride (Rhône – Poulenc, Mumbai). Histamine dihydrochloride was dissolved in distilled water and desired concentrations were prepared. The test drug Chlerodendrum inerme concentration was 100microgram per ml prepared by suspending with 2% CMC and then the volume was adjusted to 10 ml with normal saline for making the concentration of 100 µg/ml.in distilled water.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted after the approval of the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) (IAEC/SSSMCRI/2018-05). The study followed the Helsinki Declaration. The seeds of Tridax procumbance were obtained from a forest near the experimental institute. These fresh seeds were thoroughly cleaned with water to remove dirt. Seeds were dried for one week in the shed. After complete drying, the seeds were powdered. The powder was packed in a sealed bottle and stored in a dry, cool, and dark place.

The extract is prepared with the help of Soxhlet's apparatus (hot extraction) and extracted with 95% ethanol at a temperature of 60°-80°C. Ethanolic

extract was subjected to filtration. It was then dried under reduced pressure to obtain a solid mass that was free from the solvent. The dried extract was dissolved in distilled water.

Drugs used were Histamine diphosphate (Sigma Chemical, USA) and Promethazine hydrochloride (Rhône – Poulenc, Mumbai). Histamine dihydrochloride was dissolved in distilled water and desired concentrations were prepared. The test drug Chlerodendrum inerme concentration was 100microgram per ml prepared by suspending with 2% CMC and then the volume was adjusted to 10 ml with normal saline for making the concentration of 100 µg/ml.in distilled water.

Animals were divided into four groups of six animals each. Each animal were served as its own control. Animals belonging to each group were subjected to a histamine aerosol (0.2% Histamine diphosphate in saline) using a glass nebulizer for 2 sec in an airtight Perspex chamber. Aerosolization of the solution was achieved via a compressed air line operating at a pressure of 8 Psi and a flow rate of 5ml/min. After exposure to the histamine aerosol, the animal showed signs of immediate immobilization and bouts of coughing. This was followed by shallow breathing symptoms, after which the animal collapsed, fell on its back and convulsed. The time taken by the animal to fall on its back after exposure to the aerosol was designated as the exposition time. The exposition time for each animal in all the four groups was noted [12, 13]. Once the animal fell on its back, it was immediately taken out of the chamber and exposed to fresh air where the animal returned back to normal. After 1 hour the animals in the first three groups were administered orally 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg p.o, of Chlerodendrum inerme respectively. While the fourth group of animals received 300µg/kg of Promethazine by oral route. One hour later, the animals were reexposed to the aerosol and exposition time for each animal was noted. The difference in the exposition time before and after Chlerodendrum inerme administration was taken as a measure of the protective effect. Percent protection afforded by the Chlerodendrum inerme was calculated by the formula.

Percentage Protection = $\frac{E_{ta} - E_{tb}}{E_{tb}}$

Where 'Eta' is the mean exposition time after treatment with extract and 'Etb' is the mean exposition time before treatment with extract.

GROUP I	–Asthmatic control-0.5% Histamine HCL aerosol.			
GROUP III	Dose (100mg/kg) of aqueous ethanolic extract of <i>Chlerodendrum inerme</i>)			
GROUP III	Dose (200mg/kg) of aqueous ethanolic extract of <i>Chlerodendrum inerme</i>)			
GROUP IV	Standard treatment	0.5% Histamine	HCL aerosol	with Mepyramine (8mg/ kg.p.o)

Each animal was then individually placed gently on Eddy's hot plate at 55°C. Latency to exhibit nociceptive responses such as licking paws or jumping off the hot plate were determined at 30, 60, 90 and 120 min after administration of the drugs or vehicle.

Data were entered on a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and statistically analyzed statically using the SPSS-20 software. Unpaired student t-tests were used to compare reaction times. A p-value of 0.05 or less than 0.05 is indicated as statistically significant.

Observations and Results

No animals died during the acute toxicity test, nor were any adverse effects detected in animals treated with *Chlerodendrum inerme* at 2000 mg/kg. This indicates that the drug is nearly nontoxic in mice up to an oral dose of 2.0 g/kg of body weight. One by twentieth,

The mean reaction time of all three groups, i.e., control, standard & test groups, at all time points is illustrated in Table 1. Compared to animals treated with saline, the mean reaction time of the aspirin and extract-treated group was increased, as shown in Figure 1. one tenth and one fifth of dose was selected

from acute toxicity study and administered to animals. Histamine when inhaled has been shown to induce bronchoconstriction by direct H1 receptor activation and also by a naturally mediated bronchoconstrictors effect via vagal reflexes results in preconvulsive dyspnea and it also may lead to the appearance of convulsions. In the present study of *Chlerodendrum inerme* have been shown the significant increase in pre-convulsion time due to pre-treatment with *Chlerodendrum inerme* at the dose of 100, 200 and 500mg/kg of body weight of guinea pigs, when the guinea pigs were exposed to histamine The percentage protection of *Chlerodendrum inerme* -100, 200, 500mg/kg is 27.43, 28.79, 29.83% and standard drug showed 50.31% respectively [Tab-2, Fig-6]. The guinea pigs exposed to histamine aerosol showed signs of progressive dyspnea leading to convulsions. The results presented here confirm the traditional claim that *Chlerodendrum inerme* confers some protection on guinea-pigs against the effects of a histamine aerosol. The immediate protection is not statistically significant but later extended, however the protection is not prolonged. Under the conditions employed, *Chlerodendrum inerme* was found to possess moderate antihistaminic activity.

Histamine aerosol induced broncho constriction in guineapigs

Group	Latent period of convulsion in seconds			
	Before	1hour	4hour	24hour
Control	16.3±2.23	18.36±0.183	18.63±0.186	18.4±0.12
<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> Ethanolic extract(100mg/kg)	16.71±1.31	29.65±.28	39.38±0.05*	28.2±0.23
<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> Ethanolic extract(200mg/kg)	15.71±0.77	30.5±3.08	40.36±1.04*	28.4±.35
Standard(CPM) (1mg/kg)	18.46±0.89	60.25±0.03*	68.26±1.01**	36.5±0.55

%Protection of the plant *Clerodendrum inerme* leaves against histamine induced broncho constriction in guineapig.

Group	%protection		
	1hour	4hour	24hour
Control(carboxymethylcellulose)	10.9	12.3	11.4
<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> ethanolicextract(100mg/kg)	43.2	57.2	40.2
<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> ethanolicextract(200mg/kg)	48	60.79	44.3
Standard(CPM)	69.76	78.3	50.1

Analgesic effect of ethanolic root extract of *Tridax Procumbance* on hot plate test in Swiss albino mice

Treatment	Pre treatmeny exposition in second	Post treatmen exposition in second	Percentage protection
<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> 100 mg	87	120	27
<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> 200 mg/kg/kg	90	127	28
Promethazine 300 mg kg	88	178	50

When the analgesic activity of aspirin and extract was compared, it was found that there was less increase in the reaction time of the group treated with extract group compared to that of the pentazocin treated group. The reaction time of the extract-treated group at 30 min was found to increase significantly compared with the pentazocin treated group. Whereas the mean reaction time of extract treated group at 60 min & 90 min was not found to be significantly increased in comparison with the standard, as shown in Table 4 & Figure 4

DISCUSSION:

On the histamine and acetylcholine chloride-induced bronchoconstriction in guinea pigs, the water extracts significantly increased the proconvulsive time in asthma relieving. They also showed significant antitussive effect through the increase of latent period of cough and inhibition of cough

Clerodendrum inerme leaf is acclaimed to treat asthma and chronic bronchitis induced by weakness of lung Qi in the view of the traditional theory of traditional Chinese medicine. In our previous study, chemical components of *Clerodendrum inerme pungens* leaf are isolated, purified, and identified. The results indicates that it mainly contains many flavonoids of which the chemical structures are characterized by quercetin, kaempferol, and isorhamnetin as aglycones linking with glycosyl groups [18, 19]. Many other researches have verified that flavonoids from Chinese herbs are

effective on antiasthmatic, antitussive, and expectorant properties, for example, naringenin from *Exocarpium Citri Grandis* and total flavones from *Acanthopanax senticosus* [26–29]. It prompted us to lay a hypothesis that these flavonoids in the three *Clerodendrum inerme* leaves might have the antiasthmatic activity. So, we analyzed the chemical components and contrasted flavonoids peaks by HPLC-DAD. The result showed that the three *Clerodendrum inerme* leaves had more similarity on overlap peaks between the 15 and 60 min and the peaks belonging to flavonoids compounds. However, due to the nature of multiple chemical constituents involved in the natural plants as well as the multifactorial condition of asthma, it is very important to further separate chemical constituents from the three *Clerodendrum inerme* leaves being effective on the relief of bronchoconstriction, inhibition of cough, and increase of secretion output. Further studies are necessary to clarify the mechanism by which the three *Clerodendrum inerme* leaves possess the antiasthmatic activity.

In conclusion, our study indicated that the water extracts of *Clerodendrum inerme* leaf demonstrated the significantly antiasthmatic effects *in vivo*. These effects were the important evidence for the traditional use of *Clerodendrum inerme* leaf as antiasthmatic remedy. It persuaded us to draw a conclusion that *Clerodendrum inerme* played an important role as well as to treat asthma and chronic bronchitis.

CONCLUSION:

The extract under study had a significant analgesic effect compared with the analgesic activity of control in an established analgesic screening method. The analgesic effect was peaking at 60 minutes and 90 minutes. Treating 400mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Tridax procumbance* root increases the reaction time on Eddy's hot plate. Hence, the present study concluded a significant analgesic effect of *Tridax procumbance* extract. Henceforth, the preparation of *Tridax procumbance* seed extract could be used as one of the drugs in multi-drug therapy for pain relief. Though, more research is needed in separating and describing the active compound or compounds responsible for the analgesic effect. Further work is also needed for the determination of the exact mechanism of action.

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